

Manufacture of Co-cured Integral Hat-stiffened Panel with Automate Fibre Placement

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Brief introduction of CCME

CCME@NUAA was established in 2002 and is conducting industrial focused researches on automated composite manufacture based on prepreg in China.

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Brief introduction of CCME

CCME has an independent laboratory with 800 m² and be equipped with 20 sets of self-designed facilities and 10 sets of analysis and test instrument.

There are 10 chief investigators, 13 PhD candidates and 30 master students in CCME.

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Manufacture of large-scale composite structures

Typical structure of composite parts applied in aircraft

Current manufacturing methods of composite stiffened structures

Trends in manufacturing methods of composite stiffened structures

Better interface strength between stringers and skin, greater deformations of the final part can be obtained by co-curing method.

Manufacture with high quality, low cost & automation

AFP for Skin & co-curing of skin and stringers

[1]G. Kim, 2010. [2]S. Li, 2015. [3] J. B. Patterson, 2018. [4] K.C. Shin, 2003. [5] C. Zhao, 2016. [6] L. Esposito. 2019.

Manufacture procedure of hat-stiffened composite skin

Key points of co-cured hat-stiffened panel with AFP

Optimization of AFP processing parameter

- Obtain good cohesion between prepreg with substance
- Avoid excessive out-of-plane deformation of fibre

Optimization of inner mold's material and shape

- Provide sufficient support for compaction force of AFP
- Provide uniformity curing pressure
- Achieve good surface quality
- Easy to remove

Typical defects within a hat-stiffened panel

Excessive out-of-plane deformation due to improper compaction force or insufficient support of inner mold

Uneven thickness resulting from inappropriate inner filling mold

Non-common resin flow causing by non-uniform cured pressure

Design of inner mold for co-cured hat-stiffened panel with AFP

Common inner mold for hat-stiffened panel

Mold	Advantages	Shortages
Metal	Best manufacture quality	Difficult to remove & not suit for complex hat-stiffened panels
Vacuum bag	Simple & lowest cost	Easily break leading to waste product & poor product surface
Silicone rubber/nylon	Good support, relatively uniform curing pressure and good product surface	Difficult to adjust curing pressure and remove from complex parts

Requirements of inner mold for co-cured hat-stiffened panel with AFP

- The mold should have **perfect anti-deformability**, to decrease its compressive deformation and prepreg plies' out of -plate deformation under the action of compact force, during the layup of skin by AFP.
- The mold can provide **enough and uniform curing pressure** during the co-curing process. Moreover, the **inner surface quality of stringer and skin** also should be considered.
- The mold can **be removed easily and suit for complex composite panels.**

[7]Y. Mo, 2016. [8]C. K. Huang, 2003.

Optimization of integral co-cured hat-stiffened panel with AFP

Universal inner mold for complex co-cured hat stiffened panel with AFP

AFP process		Silicone bladder + Silicone core	Silicone bladder combining with silicone core to provide sufficient support in AFP
Co-curing process		Silicon bladder + Vacuum bag	Provide uniform curing pressure Easy to remove from composite Improve product surface quality

Challenges to the process

- Fibre distribution**
- ✓ Compressive deformation of flexible inner mold,
- ✓ Compaction force
- Dimensional accuracy**
- ✓ Thermal deformation of flexible inner mold

Generation of out-of-plane fiber waviness due to compressive deformation of flexible inner mold

[9] J. Wang, 2012. [10] D. Wilhelmsson, 2018. [11] C. Ma, 2018.

Compressive Deformation of inner mold in AFP process

Key influence factors of inner mold's compressive deformation

- ❑ Elastic modulus of silicon rubber (E)
- ❑ Compaction force of AFP (F)

Compression of inner mold **decreases with an increasing of elastic modulus of silicon rubber.** When inner mold's elastic modulus is larger than that of flexible compact roller, the influence of inner mold on the compressive deformation can be ignored.

FEM of compressive deformation

Influence of silicone rubber's elastic modulus on inner mold compression

Thermal Deformation of flexible inner mold in curing process

Influence of E on the thermal deformation of flexible inner mold in curing process

The lower elastic modulus lead to desirable curing pressure & uniform thickness of final part.

- ✓ The greatest influence factor is the elastic modulus of inner flexible mold.
- ✓ Elastic modulus of inner mold should be close to that of compaction flexible roller to achieve a high manufacturing quality.

FEM of thermal deformation

ODB: Job-5-5.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-3 Tue Jun 12 22:11:51 GMT+08:00 2018

Step: Step-1
Increment: 1; Step Time = 1.000
Primary Var: U, Magnitude

$E = 2.74\text{MPa}$

ODB: Job-2-5.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-3 Tue Jun 12 22:08:11 GMT+08:00 2018

Step: Step-1
Increment: 1; Step Time = 1.000
Primary Var: U, Magnitude

$E = 5.54\text{MPa}$

ODB: Job-41.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-3 Tue Jun 12 22:26:07 GMT+08:00 2018

Step: Step-1
Increment: 1; Step Time = 1.000
Primary Var: U, Magnitude

$E = 9.39\text{MPa}$

ODB: Job-34.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-3 Wed Jun 13 15:42:37 GMT+08:00 2018

Step: Step-1
Increment: 1; Step Time = 1.000
Primary Var: U, Magnitude

$E = 11.2\text{MPa}$

ODB: Job-9-4.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-3 Tue Jun 12 22:20:19 GMT+08:00 2018

Step: Step-1
Increment: 1; Step Time = 1.000
Primary Var: U, Magnitude

$E = 14.3\text{MPa}$

Manufacture of co-cured hat-stiffened panel with AFP

Manufacture of co-cured hat-stiffened panel with AFP

Hand lay-up of stringer

Automated lay-up of skin in NUAA

Double curved hat-stiffened panel manufactured by AFP and co-curing

Observe side

Reverse side

Cross section

Experimental verification of FEA

Critical parameters in manufacturing process

- Elastic modulus of compaction roller - 5MPa
- Elastic modulus of flexible inner mold - 2.47MPa, 5.54MPa, 9.39MPa, 11.2MPa and 14.3MPa
- Passion ratio of flexible inner mold - 0.48
- Coefficient of thermal expansion - $8.51 \times 10^{-4} m/^{\circ}C$

Cross-section of hat-stiffened panels with different kinds of inner mold

E=2.47MPa

E=5.54MPa

E=9.39MPa

E=11.2MPa

E=14.3MPa

Verification Criterion

Fibre distribution

Thickness deviation

Microscopic fiber distribution of hat-stiffened panel

Fibre waviness, imperfect geometrical shape around the corner, local out-of-plane deformation of composite skin would be resulted from an oversized elastic modulus of silicon bladder.

Thickness distribution of hat-stiffened panel

Silicon bladder, which elastic modulus is 5MPa, can provide a much more uniform curing pressure than other silicon bladder and achieve a high geometric accuracy of co-cured hat-stiffened panels, which thickness deviation is smaller than 7%.

Silicon bladder's elastic modulus should be about 5MPa, which is equal to the elastic modulus of flexible roller of AFP, to improve both layup quality and curing quality.

Distribution of measure point

Thickness Distribution of hat-stiffened panel

Summary

- ❑ Hat-stiffened panel manufactured by co-curing an AFP process
- Fiber deformation
- Dimensional accuracies

- ❑ Challenge to manufacture Hat-stiffened panel with co-curing and AFP process
- Appropriate Process parameters of AFP
- Proper inner mold for enclosed cavity

- ❑ Design and process optimisation
- Compressive deformation of inner mold
- Thermal deformation of inner mold

- A integral route to prepare hat-stiffened composite panels with co-curing and AFP process
- A novel inner mold for enclosed cavity to achieve good fiber contribution and dimensional accuracies
- Satisfactory better mechanical performance and low cost

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